

THE KINDS OF TABOOS AND EUPHEMISM CONTROLLING OR RULING OVER THEM

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Annotation: This article pays great attention to the methods of teaching as well as learning how to speak the English language politely and some kinds of taboo words as dirty expressions. Several dirty words and some euphemistic terms are described widely and exactly in this article and also the teacher tries to give samples from his experience which are considered to be very important for both teachers and learners.

Key words: taboo words, dirty words, cultural, religious, food, euphemistic term, sweet words, polite, rude, cultural shock, isolated, community, relations, politeness.

The links of the communication development look like that society itself presupposes the existence of communication and the existence of the life of irreplaceable communications. People who do not want to be isolated or out of community relations try to be polite. Mostly educated persons represent as a symbol of politeness and other parents should teach their children to learn from them in every situation. In fact, people everywhere and usually tried to look for the word less negative, less awkward, to say, instead of them which were offensive, shocking and awkward. Since our early history parents have been respectful for substituting some taboos to other equivalents, the language study called it as euphemisms. Children’s skills to be able to avoid using dirty words or be able to change them to sweet ones considered as parents’ intelligence or artistic attitude towards their children’s care. As our wise ancestors cited “Qush inida ko‘rganini qiladi” The translation is “The bird

(child) can do whatever it (s/he) see at home” The child is the subject of teaching and education not only at home but also at schools, lyceums or institutions of higher education as well. While Uzbek children are showing one’s intelligence or politeness in abroad, the above mentioned representers may also take into consideration. The ethnography of euphemisms are poorly explored in Uzbek and other languages therefore there is no clear idea of what area of linguistics it is, its level of language, its language unit, its speech phenomenon, its subject matter, its visual object. In this report I am going to describe kinds of taboos and euphemism. The vital problem is to understand or to be aware of taboos and then try not to use them not only in public places but also in one’s speech. Students should know types of taboos to follow the direction given above. In this report taboos are divided into three main types such as: cultural taboos, religious taboos and food taboos. Every student must be aware of the examples of them and of course meaning or etymology of taboos.

The term taboo is of Polynesian origin (the words “tabu” or “tapu” in the Tongan language) and was introduced to the English language only in the eighteenth century. The original Polynesian term has a specific religious association—see also the famous book Totem and Taboo (Sigmund Freud 1955).² According to Encyclopedia Britannica, taboo is defined as “the prohibition of an action based on the belief that such behavior is either too sacred and consecrated or too dangerous and accursed for ordinary individuals to undertake.” Mostly taboos are specific term for fulfilling high ranked people’s wish. Time to time they serve as special way or direction for society to follow on. In the history of humanity while having no written rules some taboos can be changed or demand to be obeyed without hesitation.

A taboo is an implicit prohibition on something (usually against an utterance or behavior) based on a cultural sense that it is excessively repulsive or, perhaps, too sacred for ordinary people. Such prohibitions are present in virtually all societies. On a comparative basis, taboos, for example related to food items, to seem make no sense at all, as what may be declared unfit for one group by custom or religion may be perfectly acceptable to another.

According to the Polynesian : People may be born with one divine strength, but not slaves. It might affect others if they approached to it. The history of taboos is varied day by day and while serving on some rulers or chiefs disposal they classified into three groups: (According to the report by Nikita Calcutta University) Religious Taboo Cultural Taboo Food and Drink Taboo Religious taboos are one of the strict and basic samples of taboos. Nearly every religious representer has their own rules of activity. For example: According to Indian religious prohibitions, people must respect cows. Even eating their meat is also fiercely banned. Indian people walk with bare legs not to harm other living creatures on the earth. For Muslim people many activities are prohibited based on Koran. They are drinking alcohol, eating pig meat, staring at strange women. Respecting elderly is main aim and there are so many directions that Muslims must follow. Examples of Religious or Cultural Taboos. Many taboos are associated with religion or culture. Some of these tend to be specific to particular countries, including both developing countries and fully developed nations. Birth control — In some religions, such as Catholicism, it is considered taboo to use birth control medications or devices. Blood transfusions -Jehovah Witnesses are forbidden to undergo blood transfusions or use certain blood products. Eating beef Cows are recognized as sacred animals in India. The Hindu faith, which is the predominant religion in India, forbids consuming beef. Eating pork — Consuming pork is forbidden in some religions, including Judaism and Islam. Eating cold foods during pregnancy - Per traditional Chinese medicine, eating cold foods is off-limits for women who are pregnant.

Cultural Taboo from this term we are able to be aware of cultural differences among the society. To my mind of view the above mentioned idea is shaped from the smallest point of community as a family. All parents try to follow their children some directions that they made. Gathering and collaborating them continuously the cultural taboos are appeared in the world. Every country has their colorful unrepeated taboos , which lead to the term of “cultural shock” . Here is some examples : In New Zealand: Do not press the horn; In Japan: Do not give a tip; In France: Do not ask or talk about anything about money;

Food and Drink Taboo Many food taboos and other prohibitions forbid a specific animal's meat, including mammals, rodents, reptiles, amphibians, fish, mollusks, crustaceans and insects, which may be associated with a reaction to disgust. During certain religious occasions (e.g., Lent), at certain stages of life (e.g., pregnancy), or for certain groups of people (e.g., priests), certain food might be forbidden, even though food is otherwise allowed. On a comparative basis, within the same culture or through various cultures, what may be declared unfit for one category may be perfectly appropriate to another. Currently, food taboos usually appear to Food taboos generally seem to be meant, spiritually or physically, to protect the human being from harm, but there are several other explanations given for their presence within cultures. In several, including those who are seen as religious or spiritual in nature, an ecological or medical history is evident. Food taboos can help to make more productive use of a resource, but when applied to only a resource A food taboo accepted as part of their way by a specific community or tribe allows the group's solidarity, helps that particular group to stand out and preserve its identity in the face of others, and thus provides a sense of belonging. Teachers should teach them to be careful in using like these words in their speech while talking English and American speaking people in order not to come across to the inconvenient situations.

In UK Do not ask the income or salary of others; In fact, many intelligent or polite people try to avoid making conversation about one's salary or income. Sometimes questions like these can hear in the street as an ordinary way. For making a long and farewell communications with others never ask about their earning life status, if it is British people, it must be always out of topic. Especially, students targeting to become an interpreter want to have a nice conversation with foreigners. In this case being awareness of cultural rules may help them.

It considered bad luck for a building to have a 13th floor in the United States Education should not be limited only one network it must extend its branches to other areas of life. As our president cited “Our candidates should be competitive around the world with their opponents” Abovementioned idea is useful for builders or others specialists in this network. Even the best communication symbols of non –

verbal have some differences and not knowing them can lead to inconvenient situations as well.

For instance: America: Peace. It also used to mean “V for Victory.” China, Japan, South Korea, Taiwan, Thailand: Cute pose when being photographed. United Kingdom, South Africa, Australia, New Zealand, Ireland: It is an insult when the same gesture is made except with the back of the hand facing outward. For Arab people to say the names of their wives in front of a stranger. In this context, she (idem) explains: In addition, Edward and Guth further maintain that when they are linked to honor and honor, those neutral terms become taboo as we can see themselves. In order to further clarify this notion, they add that: the gaze of both women and sacred places is forbidden to outsiders and both are assumed to require strong male security, while they are a sign of collective and public identification in different places, women are more private property and are identified with the social identity of men.(3)

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